

ORGANIZATION AND CONTENT OF SPEECH THERAPY TRAINING FOR PUPILS WITH MENTAL RETARDATION

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Abstract. *The given article describes in detail the organization of speech therapy and correctional training, organized for the purpose of eliminating speech defects in specialized auxiliary schools and boarding schools for pupils with special educational needs (mental retardation), and its content.*

Keywords: *speech, speech defects, mentally retarded, specialized auxiliary school, speech therapy and correctional work, speech therapy examination, individual training, group training.*

It is important to suggest that at present time the problem of teaching children of special education with limited mental abilities has become more acute not only due to the need to reform education, but also due to the need to integrate them into the educational environment, and to meet the needs of all children in fully accepted by peers and other adults. Full-fledged educational activity can be formed only through sufficiently developed speech. The reason of these is that speech presupposes the level of development of certain means of language (pronunciation, grammatical structure, vocabulary) and it is necessary to be able to freely and correctly use these means for communication purposes. In recent years, the contingent of specialized auxiliary schools for pupils with special educational needs has changed significantly.

Besides that, most pupils entering such institutions have severe systemic speech disorders. Based on this, speech therapy in such educational institutions should be aimed not only at a separate defect, but also at the speech system as a whole. Organization of speech therapy classes in specialized auxiliary schools for pupils with special educational needs is organized on the basis of special methodological recommendations based on state educational requirements and is carried out in the following context:

Definitely, the beginning and end of the school year, the time and duration of holidays are determined in accordance with the established school standards. For two weeks at the beginning of September, the speech therapist checks the pupils' oral and written speech, assembles groups, small groups, determines the number of pupils who will participate in individual lessons, and on this basis draws up a schedule of lessons and a long-term plan for pupils in each group.

The duration of a lesson (taking into account the psychophysiological capabilities of pupils) is 35-40 minutes in a group, 20-25 minutes in an individual lesson.

Group training is organized as follows:

- with pupils with reading and writing disorders caused by incomplete speech development - at least 2-3 times a week.
- with pupils, whose phonetic-phonemic or phonemic side of speech is not developed - at least 2-3 times a week.
- with pupils with phonetic disorders - at least 3 times a week.
- with pupils, who stutter - at least 3 times a week.

- the 2nd level of speech underdevelopment, dysarthria, rhinolalia, alalia in pupils with speech defects - individual lessons are held at least 2-3 times a week.

According to the curriculum, 5 hours are allocated for speech therapy classes in grades 1-5. Of these, 4 hours are devoted to pupils with speech disorders, and 1 hour - to pupils with speech disorders in reading and writing. Including 3 hours are allocated for speech therapy training in grades 6. It is recommended to devote 2 hours to pupils with speech disorders and 1 hour - to pupils with reading and writing disorders. In grade 7, 2 hours are allocated for speech therapy classes, and these hours are determined by the speech therapist based on the speech abilities of the pupils and also, in other classes, the speech therapist has the right to change the allotted hours based on the speech abilities of the pupils.

Moreover, the interval for organizing individual lessons is determined taking into account the severity of the speech defect of pupils and their individual characteristics. Children are removed from the register throughout the school year with the elimination of their speech defects.

The results of the speech therapy examination are recorded in the child's speech card. In special auxiliary schools for pupils with special educational needs, the purpose of special speech therapy training to eliminate existing speech defects in children is to eliminate speech defects, as well as defects in cognitive activity in children.

It is known to everyone that speech therapy work organized in specialized auxiliary schools for pupils with special educational needs can be divided into:

1. Due to the insufficient development of the leading cognitive activity in pupils with mental retardation, the entire process of speech therapy work should be aimed at the formation of operations of analysis-synthesis, comparison, abstraction and generalization.

2. Taking into account the structure of speech disorders, speech therapy work should be carried out on the entire speech system. At each speech therapy session, not only the phonetic and phonemic aspects of speech are corrected, but also the lexical and grammatical aspects.

3. It is important that the process of speech therapy work is built on the principle of gradual formation of mental activity (P. Ya. Galperin, D. B. Elkonin, etc.). This is necessary for the transition from visual-motor and visual-figurative thinking to the internal organization of actions; the formation of speech actions should be carried out in the following stages [190]:

- 1) Materialization of movement based on auxiliary means. At this stage, work on the development of sound discrimination includes the use of pictures, as well as graphic diagrams of words, where the names are analyzed. The child separates sound from the word and places the corresponding colors (vowel - red, consonant - blue) in the cells corresponding to a certain sound.

- 2) Performing an action verbally. At this stage, the child pronounces the word and, based on his auditory or kinesthetic sense, determines the presence of a particular sound in the word, without relying on auxiliary means.

- 3) Implementation of actions according to the internal plan. At this stage, the child distinguishes sounds, without material and speech support, according to his imagination.

In speech therapy work with pupils with mental retardation, a step-by-step, consistent transition from one stage to another is necessary, which is associated with the peculiarities of the pupils' mental activity [88].

4. Maximum activation of the analyzer, activation of its sense organs in different modalities, as well as the use of maximum and varied manifestations. Thus, visual perception of articulation during sound production, kinesthetic sensations in hand movements, repetition of the

position of the tongue when pronouncing a certain sound help to rely on the kinesthetic sensations of the tongue, lips.

5. A differentiated approach is very important, including taking into account the peculiarities of higher nervous activity (for example, the predominance of the excitation process or the inhibition process): the mental characteristics of the student, his motor characteristics, performance, speech level.

6. Correction of speech disorders (especially pronunciation disorders) should be inextricably linked with the general motor development of the mentally retarded schoolchild and the development of primarily fine motor skills of the hands. Considering the interdependence of the development of the hand and the organs of articulation, it is advisable to include exercises that develop fine motor skills of the hands, elements of speech therapy rhythmic training, especially in the 1st grades, in the organization of speech therapy training.

7. The content of speech therapy work should correspond to the program for acquiring literacy and mastering the native language. The formation of a practical level of language knowledge is a necessary condition for understanding the patterns of language phenomena and acquiring language knowledge. Thus, speech therapy training should prepare children to master the program of their native language.

8. Since old conditioned reflex connections in pupils with mental retardation are very conservative and difficult to change, they require careful work, especially at the stages of consolidating correct speech skills [88].

9. Repetition of the same materials in the content and form of speech therapy training makes training boring and destroys the child's interest.

10. In mentally retarded pupils, the correct speech skills acquired in speech therapy training are lost in other situations, in other speech material. Therefore, it is very important to consolidate correct speech skills in various situations (children, conversations with adults, talking on the phone, repeating what has been read, repeating independently, etc.).

11. Considering that mentally retarded pupils quickly get tired and tend to be slow, it is necessary to transfer the child from one type of work to another, frequently changing types of activity.

12. Tasks and speech material are determined by the need to gradually complicate the speech material, taking into account the characteristics of the cognitive activity of pupils with mental retardation.

13. During speech therapy sessions, the child must clearly understand the purpose of the session. Therefore, the learning objectives must be presented to the mentally retarded student in a very clear, convenient, understandable form.

14. Effective acquisition of correct speech skills by pupils with mental retardation requires a certain, not too fast pace of work.

15. It is necessary to maintain the interest of mentally retarded pupils in the correction of their speech and influence their emotional sphere.

16. Due to persistent speech impairment in mentally retarded pupils, speech therapy work in a special (correctional) auxiliary school is carried out over a longer period of time than work with healthy children.

17. Underdeveloped control and weakness of volitional processes in pupils with mental retardation require close interaction between speech therapists, teachers, educators and parents.

18. In order to implement a comprehensive medical and pedagogical approach and create favorable conditions for eliminating speech disorders, the speech therapist should work in close cooperation with medical personnel [117]

19. The school speech therapist's assistant should pay great attention to agitation among teachers, educators and parents, taking into account the duration of speech therapy works with pupils.

In conclusion, it should be suggested that the program of speech therapy training is built on a cyclical principle and includes a high repetition of lexical topics in each lesson (while speech material, sound analysis and forms of synthesis are improved).

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